

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

**D4.3 Socio-environmental Assessment of Last-mile and Edge
Technological Solutions**

Version 1

Lead Authors: Hatem Chouchane (WUR)

Daoud Urdu (WUR)

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Lead Author (s)	Hatem Chouchane (WUR); Daoud Urdu (WUR)		
Contributors	Annabel Oosterwijk (WUR); Trond Selnes (WUR); Katrine Soma (WUR)		
Internal reviewer(s)	Ioannis Neokosmides (INC), Chartsias Konstantinos Panteleimon (ICOM)		

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#	Participant Organisation Name	Short name	Country
1	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	ICCS	EL
2	BENCO BALTIC DOO ZA SAVJETOVANJE IUSLUGE	BENCO	HR
3	CAFA TECH OU	CAFA	EE
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7	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA	I2CAT	ES
8	INCITES CONSULTING SA	INC	LU
9	INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS	ICOM	EL
10	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAIN	EL
11	REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RDFCM	EL
12	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
13	UAB ART21	ART	LT
14	ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH	ZSI	AT
15	TELEFONICA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA	TID	ES
16	Astrocast SA	ASTRO	CH
17	JONATHAN MICHAEL SMITH	JS	UK

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
4G	4th Generation of broadband cellular network technology
5G	5th Generation of broadband cellular network technology
BA	Benefit Analysis
CAP	A product based on the exploitation of the results of CAPTAIN Horizon 2020 project, aims to become a gentle companion and caregiver inside the older person's house, providing a radically new hardware and software solution based on user's detection and generation of projections.
CFs	Characterization Factors
EC	European Commission
EcRL	Economic Readiness Level
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EIRA	European Interoperability Reference Architecture
E-LCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
FMIS	Farm Management Information System
G&S	Goal and Scope
GHG	Greenhouse gas
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ICT-AGRI-FOOD	Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Agriculture, and Food
IIAM	Interoperability Impact Assessment Model
IMT	Interoperability Maturity Tools
IoE	Internet of Everything
IoT	Internet of Things
IP S-LCIA	Impact Pathway Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KFT	Knowledge Facilitation Tool
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
OAT	One-at-A-Time

OSOR	Open Source Observatory
PDF	Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database
R&D	Research and Development
ROI	Return on investment
RS S-LCIA	Reference Scale Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment
SDC	Sustainable Development and Climate
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHDB	Social Hostspot DataBase
SIQAT	Structural Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit
S-LCA /SCLA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
S-LCI	Social Life Cycle Inventory
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SSI	Structural Semantic Interconnections
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
WCED	World Commission on Environment and Development
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
WSD	Word Sense Disambiguation
XGain	Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable addresses the socio-economic and environmental implications of employing advanced last-mile connectivity and edge technology solutions in various sectors across Europe. The increasing demand for these technologies and the potential ramifications of not carefully considering their environmental and socio-economic impacts underscores the urgency of this theme. The potential risks of neglecting these impacts include the exacerbation of socio-economic disparities, environmental degradation, and digital divides.

The core purpose of this deliverable is to formulate a comprehensive methodological blueprint for gauging the impacts of these technologies. This is achieved by setting forth principles for establishing study boundaries, enabling data interoperability, and structuring the impact assessment. To enable a comprehensive evaluation, this blueprint includes diverse analytical tools such as environmental footprint assessments, Social Life Cycle Assessments, benefit analysis, and assessments of economic readiness levels.

Several use cases, including livestock monitoring in Belgium, precision farming in Spain, and e-healthcare support in Greece, are presented to illustrate the potential benefits of last-mile connectivity and edge solutions. These benefits include enhancing service provision, reducing costs, and mitigating environmental impacts. While the present deliverable, D4.3, primarily focuses on outlining the methodology for these impact assessments, it also lays a strong foundation for the forthcoming Deliverable, D4.4. In D4.4, the actual impact assessment will be conducted, which will involve in-depth investigations into the practical applicability and potential impacts of these technologies.

Given the transformative potential of last-mile connectivity and edge technology solutions, the report emphasizes the need for a systematic and thorough methodology to evaluate their impacts. The meticulous approach adopted in this deliverable is integral to implementing these technologies in a manner that is not only sustainable and economically beneficial but also socially responsible across Europe.

Ultimately, the present deliverable offers a substantial foundation for forthcoming research, detailing a comprehensive methodology for gauging the imminent socio-economic and environmental impacts of implementing these technologies. As such, it acts as a vital stepping stone towards envisioning a more sustainable, inclusive, and technologically advanced future in Europe.

2 Introduction

This XGain Deliverable, D4.3, focuses on the design of a comprehensive methodology for assessing the socio-economic and environmental implications of last mile connectivity and emerging edge technologies. These technologies, augmented by enabling tools such as drones, hold the potential to improve connectivity, particularly in remote areas. The primary objective is to develop a methodological blueprint for evaluating how these technologies can enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and support improved decision-making processes for various stakeholders while carefully considering the associated socio-economic and environmental impacts.

This objective aligns directly with the broader aspirations of the XGain project, which emphasizes the promotion of sustainable and inclusive technological innovation. By developing a methodology to evaluate the direct benefits of these edge technologies for rural communities, D4.3 contributes to the wider ambition of bridging the digital divide and democratizing access to transformative technologies.

In line with XGain's commitment to sustainability and responsible innovation, a critical component of this Deliverable will be the design of the assessment of the environmental and social implications of these technologies. This entails maintaining a delicate balance between the potential socio-economic and environmental advantages of technological innovation and their accompanying consequences, with an overarching goal of achieving sustainable economic growth.

Our research approach involves a meticulous and critical review of the current literature focusing on edge technologies and their application in various sectors, with a particular emphasis on agriculture. This review will allow us to establish a solid understanding of the current state of the art in terms of technological developments and their environmental, and socio-economic implications.

Following this, the methodology will aim to encompass both potential negative and positive impacts, addressing concerns related to job displacement, privacy, environmental sustainability, as well as economic benefits. The methodology will recommend the use of environmental footprint analyses and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) for a comprehensive evaluation of the total environmental and social impacts. Additionally, it will include economic impact assessment methods, such as economic benefit analysis and economic readiness levels, to assess the economic implications of these technologies. This multifaceted approach will facilitate a holistic understanding of both immediate and cumulative effects within the broader socio-economic context.

Moreover, the deliverable will detail the approach to investigate the economic impacts tied to these last-mile connectivity and edge technologies. This approach will incorporate the application of these technologies across various real-world use case scenarios within the XGain project, aiming to provide tangible and practical insights and foster the transition towards sustainable digitalization.

Further, the support of decision-making to achieve sustainability goals comes with challenges to integrate, share and use data for assessing sustainability indicators. However, these data are not always available or lack findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (FAIR) (Wilkinson et al., 2016). For example, interoperability of data could enable new, advanced, types of analysis. Within the food and agricultural value chains, impact assessments could be possible by sharing data that are stored in several information systems across inter- and intra-organizational parts of the chain. Examples of these data are primary and secondary data to perform Life Cycle Assessments (LCA). Interfaces supporting data integration and interoperability principles are key for designing and evaluating food- and agricultural policy and information systems (Poppe et al., 2013; Kruize et al., 2015; Poppe et al., 2023).

Therefore, D4.3 will detail key mechanisms of interoperability and the importance of semantics in sharing data for sustainability impact assessments. The understanding of interoperability will shed light on how the benefits of technologies can be maximized, and potential risks minimized, through effective data integration within XGain use cases.

By critically outlining the methodological blueprint for assessing the spectrum of impacts associated with the adoption and integration of edge technologies, D4.3 provides a solid foundation for the forthcoming deliverable D4.4, in which the actual assessment will be conducted. Through this the XGain project can help steer the path towards responsible, sustainable innovation, maximizing benefits for all stakeholders involved. It is necessary to approach the assessment in this holistic manner – incorporating environmental and socio-economic aspects – to ensure that all potential implications are taken into account and that the path towards digital sustainability is well-informed and balanced.

2.1 Background and context: digital sustainability requires interoperability

Technological advances have led to the development of innovative solutions that can radically change the way we, as humans, live and simultaneously with computers (inter)operate. Edge computing, facilitating swift data processing, last-mile connectivity, and provision of high-speed, low-latency communications have substantially influenced rural communities and the agricultural sector (Javaid et al., 2022). These advancements, including drones and Internet of Things (IoT) devices, bolster efficiency and curtail agricultural expenditure. For instance, drones enable real-time livestock monitoring and data collection of crops, allowing farmers to make more informed decisions about crop management and animal welfare (Wolfert et al., 2017). These technological innovations aid farmers and other stakeholders in identifying and addressing problems faster and more efficiently, reducing the need for multiple inspections and monitoring and ultimately resulting in higher productivity and lower environmental and socio-economic costs.

The development of these technologies enables a new class of data-based services and applications that can take advantage of these technologies with low latency and high bandwidth across value chains. These data-based services are of paramount importance for sustainability assessments and require available data. However, to reap the benefits and minimise the development costs, these technologies within the value chains must interoperate with each other and share data in a semantically meaningful way. A lack of data interoperability is often regarded as one of the main obstacles towards the adoption of these technological advances (Kalatzis, et al., 2019). Although interoperability is often associated with the minimization of impacts and the maximization of benefits, the impact of interoperability for digital sustainability is often understudied.

As with any emerging technology, it is critical to holistically evaluate the potential *social, economic and environmental* impacts that might occur. Until now, far too little attention has been paid to these impacts, especially the negative aspects of technology in rural agricultural areas while considering its *interoperability* mechanisms. The interoperability mechanisms should ensure the integration of systems and data easily and securely while addressing obstacles to the adoption of new technologies and therefore contribute to digital sustainability. The interoperability approach, as part of the integrated impact, will be detailed in Chapter 7.

This lapse in consideration carries significant risks. Neglecting a comprehensive assessment could lead to unintended and potentially harmful consequences such as exacerbating socio-economic inequalities, causing environmental harm, and deepening the digital divide. These are all scenarios we might face if we don't pay serious attention to the integrative impacts of new technologies in rural areas.

Given this, the primary focus of this deliverable, D4.3, is to rectify this oversight by developing a robust methodological blueprint for evaluating the full spectrum of impacts associated with these technologies (e.g., environmental, social and economic). The methodology aims to encompass both the potential benefits and drawbacks, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the implications and assisting in the proactive mitigation of negative effects. By doing so, we aim to help steer the path towards the responsible adoption and integration of such technologies.

A formulation of comprehensive socio-economic and environmental impact assessment is crucial for understanding the potential effects of these technologies on farms, communities, and regions (Kraus et al., 2020; Yawson and Frimpong-Wiafe, 2018; Park et al., 2018). Such an assessment, to be undertaken in the subsequent Deliverable D4.4, will facilitate the identification of potential negative consequences, enabling preemptive measures to mitigate associated risks, while highlighting the potential benefits.

For instance, the use of drones for crop monitoring might lead to the displacement of human workers. Additionally, the incorporation of these technologies might raise valid concerns about the potential impact on privacy and security. Equally important is the consideration of the entire life cycle of these technologies, such as their energy consumption. It becomes necessary to ensure that the environmental consequences of these technologies do not outweigh their benefits.

However, it is important to note that this deliverable, D4.3, does not undertake the actual assessment. Instead, it lays out the comprehensive methodology that will be used in the subsequent deliverable, D4.4, to guide such assessments, providing a robust foundation for future impact evaluations.

2.2 Framework and Direction of the Report

This report, embracing a holistic approach, is primarily driven by developing a methodological blueprint to evaluate the potential of connectivity and last-mile edge technologies in the rural context, specifically across various sectors. This involves probing how these technologies can enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and enable evidence-based decision-making processes within these sectors.

Firstly, our approach focuses on unearthing the considerable advantages that these technologies might bring across different sectors in rural communities. Simultaneously, it is equally important to acknowledge the potential adverse socio-economic and environmental impacts that could surface.

Secondly, a key aspect of our framework is to underscore the potential of these technologies in closing the digital divide and democratizing access to advanced technological tools. This initiative is essential for fostering inclusive growth and development across different sectors in rural areas.

Aligned with the principles of responsible innovation and sustainability of XGain, thirdly, we establish a foundation for evaluating the environmental and social impacts that may accompany the adoption and integration of these technologies. This groundwork confirms that technological advancements in these areas align with the goals of environmental conservation, social equity and economic viability.

Not limited to presenting facts, this report is designed to enhance the understanding of various stakeholders, including policymakers, tech developers, and rural communities, regarding the state-of-the-art in edge technologies and their application across different sectors. It provides a methodological blueprint for future comprehensive assessments, including an environmental footprint analysis, a Social Life Cycle Assessment

(SLCA), and an economic impact assessment. These detailed evaluations will be conducted in the subsequent Deliverable D4.4.

Lastly, our strategy involves leveraging the insights derived from these methodological foundations to craft strategies for maximizing benefits and mitigating potential negative impacts. This includes exploring ways to enhance interoperability and promote meaningful data sharing across these technologies, thereby facilitating the adoption and utilization of these technological advancements.

By crafting a methodological approach for addressing the challenges of achieving digital sustainability, this Deliverable provides a springboard for the in-depth evaluations and assessments to be carried out in the next phase.

2.3 Mapping XGain Outputs

As the digital revolution unfolds, XGain stands dedicated to closing the digital divide, always upholding the critical importance of sustainability. The envisioned future is one where digital tools penetrate all sectors, such as healthcare, agriculture, education, and more. However, the glaring disparities in the digital sphere cannot be overlooked. Urban societies, backed by robust digital infrastructure, are thriving, while rural communities are wrestling with escalating inequalities due to a deficit in necessary digital resources. The overarching objective of XGain is the delivery of a Knowledge Facilitation Tool. This tool is designed to facilitate the development of business models and aid decision-making in the selection of a technology ecosystem, consisting of connectivity options and edge processing solutions. XGain pursues a multi-actor and practitioner-oriented approach, conducting comprehensive assessments of socio-economic and techno-environmental impacts of these technologies.

Key aims of XGain's project include bolstering systemic resilience and energy efficiency, contributing to climate mitigation, and diminishing the digital divides between different types of citizens, farms, sectors, and regions. With a focus on specific emerging edge technologies such as drones and IoT devices, XGain's efforts are aimed at improving efficiency and decision-making in sectors such as agriculture, while concurrently evaluating socio-economic and environmental implications.

The core objective of this deliverable, D4.3, is to develop a comprehensive methodological blueprint for evaluating the potential of last-mile edge technologies and connectivity in the rural context, particularly across sectors such as agriculture. This involves investigating how these technologies can enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and facilitate evidence-based decision-making processes within these sectors. The actual assessment using this methodological blueprint will be performed in the subsequent deliverable, D4.4.

The potential socio-economic and environmental implications, both beneficial and harmful, are largely dictated by the specific applications of these technologies. Consider the example of livestock monitoring. Replacing physical animal inspections with drone and camera surveillance can lead to positive environmental impacts like reduced carbon footprint due to decreased transportation needs. This shift also brings an economic advantage by cutting down transportation-related costs and potentially reducing labour costs, as the need for human involvement in routine checks lessens. On the social front, benefits may include improved animal health due to continuous monitoring and early illness detection, stress reduction for farmers managing sick animals, and increased availability for other tasks due to the reduction in physical inspection requirements.

Nevertheless, we must also anticipate inevitable negative social repercussions, such as increased dependence on these technologies by farmers. This could result in farmers relying solely on cameras and drones, overlooking

the necessity for occasional physical inspections. Additionally, drone usage may raise privacy concerns for neighbouring residents.

This deliverable aligns with XGain's broader aspirations of promoting sustainable and inclusive technological innovation. By investigating the tangible benefits of edge technologies for rural communities, we contribute to the larger aim of bridging the digital divide and democratizing access to transformative technologies.

Further, the deliverable integrates our commitment to sustainable and responsible innovation. We strive to strike a delicate balance between the potential benefits of technological innovation and their accompanying environmental and social consequences. To achieve this, we employ rigorous methodologies including environmental footprint analyses and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA).

Additionally, we delve into data interoperability and the semantic sharing of data, to maximize the benefits of these technologies and minimize potential drawbacks. Through a holistic approach, XGain aims to harmonize the available data of technological innovation to assess their accompanying environmental and social impacts. The ultimate vision is a future where digital resources are distributed equitably, ensuring no community is left behind in the digital revolution while considering its social, environmental and economic impact.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D4.3 Socio-environmental Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions

Socio-environmental assessment of last-mile and edge technological solutions (1st version)

TASKS			
T4.2 Socio-environmental Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions	T 4.2 is devoted to uncovering the socio-economic and environmental consequences of connectivity and edge technologies, along with the following services they facilitate, all within a framework of sustainable socio-economic and environmental practices. A key area of this investigation is understanding how	Ch 2: Introduction Ch 3: XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment approach Ch 4: Environmental impact assessment Ch 5: Social impact assessment Ch 6: Economic impact assessment Ch 7: Interoperability analyses.	In this initial iteration of deliverable D4.3, the groundwork is laid for the methodologies that will be implemented for the socio-economic and environmental assessments and data interoperability. The final version of the deliverable (D4.4) will be devoted to detailing the findings and their interpretations across these three crucial domains.

	<p>drones, as an instance of these technologies, can optimize the use of natural resources in agriculture in a sustainable manner.</p>	<p>Ch 8: XGain Use cases Ch 9: Conclusion and recommendations</p>	
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2.4 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The initial iteration of this deliverable serves as a foundation for the forthcoming analysis, introducing the comprehensive methodology planned for the socio-economic and environmental assessments, the study boundaries and data interoperability. In line with this, Chapter 3 is dedicated to elucidating the integrated sustainability impact assessment approach aimed at understanding the socio-economic and environmental implications of connectivity and edge technologies, as well as their associated interoperability. The methodology for the environmental impact assessment will be expounded in Chapter 4, while Chapter 5 delves into the social assessment approach. Chapter 6 will be centred around the economic assessment, Chapter 7 provides guidelines for case study analyses and deliberates on interoperability considerations, and Chapter 8 elaborates on Use Case specifications and expected socio-economic and environmental impacts.

3 XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment approach

A total of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were defined in 2015 (WHO, 2015) to improve the well-being of human lives and our planet around the world, including, among others, the goals aiming for; building resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation (SDG9), reducing inequalities (SDG10), as well as improving responsible consumption and production (SDG12), climate action (SDG13) and life on land (SDG15). These carefully formulated and agreed goals are based on work stemming back to 1987 when the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) defined sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). The sustainability paradigm allows thinking about pathways for an intervened environmental, societal and economical approach for improving quality of life. Accordingly, digital sustainability is the implementation of technologies considering key drivers that have the potential to achieve high ecological-economic-social gains (sustainability) (Bag et al., 2021).

In this research, we employ an XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment approach for combining multiple impact assessment methods, encompassing environmental, social, and economic sustainability dimensions. Moreover, for digital sustainability, interoperability is crucial because it refers to a computer system or software's ability to exchange and use the information provided by the environmental and socio-economic impact assessments (Sheth, 1999). As such, interoperability is a pre-condition for digital sustainability because the data inputs and outputs of the impact assessments are facilitated to reach the users of the data, which then are available for making informed decisions by various stakeholders.

This all-encompassing perspective ensures a comprehensive understanding of the effects of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies and their enabled services. This multi-dimensional understanding of the impact is vital for strategizing sustainable digital implementation.

In XGain's integrated sustainability impact assessment approach, we use a mix of both quantitative and qualitative methods, as illustrated in Figure 1. The quantitative techniques are set to be used for environmental footprint assessments and economic impact analyses. Concurrently, qualitative methods will be leveraged for social impact assessments. For case study analyses, we will utilize a blended approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods, as appropriate, to ensure a comprehensive analysis of each specific case. The specifics of these methodologies are explained further in the upcoming chapters of this deliverable. This multi-method approach ensures all aspects of the technologies' impacts are thoroughly captured. It's important to note that this deliverable, D4.3, establishes the methodological blueprint for the assessments. The actual application of these methodologies and the detailed assessment will be conducted in the subsequent deliverable, D4.4. This sequential approach ensures the robustness of the methodological blueprint before carrying out the practical assessments.

The XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment approach promoting digital sustainability in the agricultural sector of Europe, with emphasis on the rural areas, comprehensively captures the current state of knowledge and research covering multidimensional impact assessments focusing on environmental, economic, and social impacts of connectivity and edge technologies with a focus on interoperability.

Figure 1: Dimensions for XGain sustainability assessment approach, including environmental, social and economic assessment methods, as well as the interoperability analyses (quantitative and qualitative)

3.1 Goal and scope of the assessment

The overarching goal of this assessment is to evaluate the socio-economic and environmental impacts of implementing last-mile connectivity and edge technologies, along with their enabled services.

On the socio-economic front, the direct and indirect implications of technology adoption will be examined. Direct outcomes may include reduced labour and transportation costs in sectors such as livestock monitoring, courtesy of increased use of drones and camera surveillance. Indirect social benefits might encompass improved animal health from continuous monitoring, and enhanced farmer productivity due to less time spent on physical inspections.

From an environmental and biodiversity perspective, the assessment will apply the environmental footprint methodology, particularly focusing on the use phase of these technologies. We will measure and evaluate their impacts on various facets of the Earth's biophysical systems, including climate change, resource cycles, water resource uses, and effects on biodiversity. This approach ensures that these technologies' repercussions remain within the planet's safe operational boundaries.

Potential negative social impacts, such as increased technology dependency and privacy concerns, will also be considered. The overarching objective is to formulate strategies that maximize benefits while minimizing potential drawbacks, with the understanding that specific applications and contexts significantly influence these impacts.

3.2 Functional unit

The functional unit in an assessment is essential as it serves as a defined measure of the performance of the systems being evaluated, creating the foundation for all further calculations. This benchmark becomes particularly crucial when comparing different systems or scenarios, guaranteeing comparability and fairness in the evaluations.

In the setting of examining the socio-economic and environmental impacts of last-mile connectivity and edge computing technologies, a suitable functional unit is of paramount importance. Given that these technologies are primarily operational during their use phase, a time-based functional unit appears to be the most pertinent.

Therefore, "one hour of use" is selected as the functional unit for this assessment. This unit captures the impacts associated with one hour of operating the connectivity and edge technologies and their enabled services. It accounts for the cumulative impacts over time, with a significant portion of these impacts arising during active usage.

The merit of this functional unit is its broad applicability across various scenarios, assuring consistency throughout the assessment. However, care must be taken to ensure this choice doesn't mask important differences in usage patterns and impacts across distinct contexts and applications. The overarching aim is a balanced assessment that facilitates meaningful comparisons and inferences.

3.3 System boundaries

Defining a system boundary is a critical step in assessing socio-economic and environmental impacts. Determining the scope of the analysis and explicitly outlining what falls within the system boundary is essential (Tillman et al., 1994). Usually, such an assessment encompasses a product or process's entire lifecycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal or recycling, often referred to as a "cradle-to-grave" approach (Finnveden et al., 2009). However, system boundaries can be adapted to suit the analysis' specific needs, and it is vital to transparently convey any assumptions or limitations in the boundary definition (Ekvall and Weidema, 2004; Finnveden et al., 2009).

Figure 2 illustrates the categorization of system boundaries for connectivity, edge technologies and enabled services into three levels. Level 0 covers the complete life cycle of these technologies, from the cradle to the grave. The cradle phase comprises the extraction, manufacturing, and assembly of materials needed to develop last-mile connectivity, ICT infrastructure such as base stations, routers and data centres, and end-user devices and premises, such as drones, cameras, sensors, and monitoring devices. Conversely, the grave phase addresses the end-of-life stage for these products, including disassembly, waste management, landfill, and recycling processes.

Level 1 focusses on the environmental impacts of connectivity and edge technologies during their use, primarily related to energy consumption and emissions (Malmodin and Lundén, 2018). This level investigates the energy and carbon emissions associated with various connectivity types (e.g., 4G, 5G, Wi-Fi, satellite internet, LoRaWAN) and ICT infrastructure such as base stations, routers, data centres, etc. (Yan et al., 2013).

Lastly, Level 2 delves into the diverse services enabled by last-mile communication and edge technologies implementation. These services cover areas such as image processing, livestock monitoring, crop spraying and monitoring, and artificial intelligence applications and their related end-user devices (drones, sensors, cameras, etc). This level seeks to understand and evaluate the implications of these services within the broader context of their respective industries and the environment.

Our analysis primarily encompasses Level 1 and Level 2, which address the use phase of connectivity and edge technologies, and their associated enablers and end-users' devices. This focus aligns with XGain's core interest in assessing the impacts arising from the operative stages of these technologies and their related services.

Figure 2: System boundaries and environmental, social and economic impact levels for connectivity and edge technologies

4 Environmental impact assessment

4.1 An overview

In order to evaluate the environmental impact of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies, along with the services they enable, we employ the comprehensive environmental footprint assessment methodology. This approach offers a systematic way to quantify and examine the extent to which these specific technologies and their applications utilize natural resources and contribute to environmental pressures.

Footprint indicators form an essential link between human activities and the concept of planetary boundaries. These boundaries outline the safe operational limits for humanity within the Earth's biophysical systems. The footprint indicators provide a quantifiable measure of the environmental pressures and impacts arising from resource use and emissions. To prevent undesirable environmental changes, the goal is not just to diminish these footprints, but also to ensure they stay within the planetary boundaries (Fang et al., 2015).

The 'footprint family' is a concept that encompasses an environmental impact analysis that integrates multiple footprints, thereby capturing the potential trade-offs and shifting burdens between different environmental pressures. This comprehensive approach can provide policymakers with invaluable insights into the sustainability of specific practices or technologies (Fang and Heijungs, 2014; Fang et al., 2014; Fang et al., 2016; Vanham et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Environmental footprint family and their linked planetary boundaries (source: Vanham et al., 2019)

The 'environmental footprint family' is a comprehensive collection of these indicators, tracking these pressures from various perspectives (Figure 3). It encompasses the carbon footprint, energy footprint, water footprint, nitrogen footprint and phosphorus footprint, among others, which are intrinsically tied to urgent global issues such as climate change, freshwater use, and energy security (Fang et al., 2014). Additionally, Vanham et al., (2019) broadened this set to include other critical indicators like the land footprint and biodiversity footprint.

Within the scope of this part of the assessment, which is focused on the environmental impacts of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies, these footprint indicators are critical. By identifying and analyzing the environmental footprints of these technologies, we can understand their effect on different planetary boundaries, including those related to climate change, resource cycles, water resource uses, and, importantly, biodiversity. This holistic understanding allows for the formulation of strategies that ensure the adoption and advantages of these technologies align with the foundational principles of environmental sustainability.

Each footprint is characterized by two distinct aspects: size and depth. The 'size' of the footprint corresponds to the volume of natural capital flows being utilized or appropriated. Conversely, 'depth' is an indication of the extent to which these natural capital flows are depleted or diminished (Niccolucci et al., 2009). While the size quantifies the exerted environmental pressures, the depth serves as a metric to quantify the consequential impacts arising from these pressures. This dual quantification allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the various footprints' influence on the environment and their long-term sustainability implications.

In order to achieve this end, the careful selection of contextually relevant footprints becomes a necessity, as highlighted by Vanham et al. (2019). This process results in the formation of a 'contextualized footprint family' tailored to the particular subject under study. For the purpose of this assessment, which focuses on last-mile connectivity and edge technologies, the footprint indicators to be incorporated will be chosen based on their direct relevance to the specific impacts these technologies and their use may precipitate. This targeted selection process guarantees that the assessment captures a wide-ranging and pertinent array of environmental impacts, thereby facilitating a thorough and precise understanding of the sustainability implications associated with these technologies.

The footprint sizes, denoting the appropriation of natural capital flows, are calculated using methodologies drawn from existing literature specific to each measured footprint. Simultaneously, the assessment will consider footprint depths, indicative of the depletion of natural capital flows, exclusively in terms of biodiversity impacts. As such, the evaluation includes footprints related to energy use, carbon emissions, water use and nutrient release. The computation of biodiversity impact adheres to the LC-IMPACT 1.2 method (Verones et al., 2020), which involves applying empirically-based characterization factors (CFs). These facilitate the translation of resource use (e.g., impact per m³ of water used) and emissions (e.g., impact per tonne CO₂ equivalent) into a measurable dimension of biodiversity impact (Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species; PDF).

The process of assessment will adhere to the outlined framework in Figure 4. For each use case, a preliminary review of the specific requirements, deployed connectivity, edge technologies, and ICT infrastructure will be carried out. After this evaluation, an examination of the system boundary for each particular case will be conducted. If deemed necessary, adjustments will be made to better tailor the boundary to the specific use case and connectivity conditions. The next stage will comprise an inventory analysis of the natural resources consumed and emissions produced, thus establishing their associated footprint sizes. The final phase involves converting these sizes into footprint depths using the LC-IMPACT methodology, represented in the Potentially

Disappeared Fraction (PDF) of species. This comprehensive approach ensures a context-sensitive and in-depth understanding of each use case’s environmental and biodiversity impacts.

Figure 4: Environmental impact assessment framework

4.2 Footprint indicators

4.2.1 Carbon Footprint

The carbon footprint is an integrative measure to quantify the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated directly and indirectly with a particular activity or accumulated throughout a product’s lifecycle, such as a device or software. This comprehensive assessment includes greenhouse gases (e.g., CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) and encapsulates each phase from the initial design and manufacturing to the final disposal or decommissioning (Pandey et al., 2011).

In the context of connectivity and edge technologies, the carbon footprint involves all the CO₂ emissions generated globally throughout digital devices and services’ production, usage, and disposal stages. This footprint includes the emissions from data centres and servers providing cloud services, the power consumption of edge

devices, as well as the manufacturing and transportation of these devices (Andrae and Edler, 2015). It's noteworthy that the carbon footprint of edge technologies also considers the CO₂ emissions generated outside the product's place of use, especially those occurring during the manufacturing and transport stages (Malmodin and Lundén, 2018).

4.2.2 Energy Footprint

The energy footprint is a significant subset of the broader ecological footprint, focusing specifically on the carbon impacts arising from energy consumption (Wiedmann, 2008). This measure can be articulated as the specific energy consumption per functional unit, incorporating both fossil fuel-derived and renewable energy sources (Sobhani et al., 2012).

When considering connectivity and edge technologies, the energy footprint can shed light on the energy efficiency of data processing, transmission, and storage solutions. It considers the energy consumed in producing these devices, their operational energy use, and their energy-related impacts during end-of-life management. The metric includes energy use across international boundaries and thus encapsulates the global impacts of energy consumption related to these technologies (Andrae and Edler, 2015). For instance, the energy footprint of a data centre would encompass the energy consumed during its construction, operation, and decommissioning, and it can vary significantly depending on factors such as the energy mix of the region and the energy efficiency of the equipment used (Malmodin and Lundén, 2018).

In this study, the computation of the energy footprint is centred solely on the use phase of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies. It primarily encompasses the direct use of energy (typically electricity) that fuels the operation of these technologies.

The energy consumption quantified in this phase is then transformed into equivalent CO₂ emissions utilizing pertinent emission factors. These factors vary depending on the type of electricity generation, and they denote the quantity of CO₂ emitted per unit of energy consumed.

Emission factors can be influenced by various factors, including the energy source (fossil fuels, renewables, etc.), technology, the efficiency of power plants, and carbon capture and storage technologies if employed. As such, the resulting CO₂ emissions may differ significantly based on the energy mix and the grid efficiency of a particular region or country.

For instance, in the context of Europe, emission factors could vary significantly across the region due to the diverse energy mix among countries. Countries heavily reliant on coal-fired power plants, for example, would have higher emission factors compared to those primarily using renewable sources like wind or solar power.

4.2.3 Water footprint

The water footprint is a critical metric that quantifies the utilisation and impacts on water resources due to human activities. Conceived by Hoekstra in 2002, it gauges both the water consumption and the subsequent impact on water quality, categorised into blue, green, and grey water footprints (Hoekstra et al., 2003; Hoekstra, 2011).

The water footprint takes on unique dimensions in the context of connectivity and edge technologies. The blue water footprint addresses water used in data centres manufacturing and cooling processes and during the operational phase of these technologies (Mytton, 2021). However, the advent of these technologies, especially

edge computing and drones, also offers opportunities to drastically reduce the water footprint in various sectors, especially agriculture.

For instance, precision agriculture, powered by edge technologies, enables efficient water use by offering real-time monitoring of soil moisture and other critical agricultural indicators. Drones equipped with sensors can provide high-resolution, timely data for image processing and detecting areas with low soil moisture. This allows for targeted irrigation, significantly reducing water waste and decreasing the agricultural sector's blue water footprint (Bwambale et al., 2022).

The water footprint assessment will adhere to the methodology delineated by Hoekstra et al. (2011) in "The Water Footprint Assessment Manual," the globally recognized standard for Water Footprint Assessment, as developed by the Water Footprint Network. Within this framework, the water footprint of a crop is defined as the cumulative volume of freshwater used during the crop growth period. The blue water footprint per unit of the crop is quantified by dividing the overall blue crop water use by the crop yield, providing a per-unit quantification of water usage.

Of particular interest in this study is the potential alteration in the water footprint following the integration of drone technology for the acquisition of high-resolution soil moisture imagery. By comparing the water footprints before and after the application of this technology, the assessment will effectively measure the impact of such technological advancements on water efficiency in agriculture.

4.2.4 Nitrogen and phosphorus footprints

Nitrogen and phosphorus are vital nutrients for all organisms, but their overuse can lead to ecological challenges such as eutrophication, acidification, and biodiversity loss (Chen et al., 2020). Here, the nitrogen and phosphorus footprints serve as significant indicators, measuring the amount of reactive nitrogen and phosphorus that end up in the atmosphere and water bodies due to human activities (Wang et al., 2011, Lu and Tian, 2017).

Edge technologies such as IoT devices and drones can play a pivotal role in monitoring and reducing these footprints, particularly in agriculture. For instance, smart farming techniques that leverage real-time soil analysis can optimize the use of nitrogen and phosphorus, preventing over-fertilization and consequently reducing the nitrogen and phosphorus footprints (Lavanya et al., 2020).

The nutrient footprint is quantified as the total nitrogen and phosphorus losses discharged into the soil and water bodies as a consequence of fertilizer application. A significant aspect of this study involves assessing the potential changes in nutrient footprints due to the application of edge technologies such as IoT devices and drones.

4.2.5 Biodiversity footprint

The biodiversity footprint, often referred to as biodiversity loss, is an aggregate measure encapsulating the cumulative impact of various potentially harmful elements, such as land and water use, chemical pollution, climate change, and invasive species (Vanham et al., 2019; Lenzen et al., 2012). These factors, associated with human consumption and production patterns, contribute directly and indirectly to biodiversity loss (Marques et al., 2019).

Edge technologies, while advantageous in many ways, also contribute to this biodiversity footprint throughout their life cycles. The production and operation of these technologies involve resource consumption, energy use, and waste generation, influencing other environmental footprints and subsequently translating into biodiversity loss (Verones et al., 2017).

However, these same-edge technologies also offer innovative solutions that can reduce their impact and enhance biodiversity conservation. For instance, IoT devices can provide real-time data about biodiversity, habitat changes, and species health, supporting more effective conservation strategies (Wägele et al., 2022). Additionally, blockchain technology can increase supply chain transparency, facilitating more sustainable consumption patterns and reducing environmental impacts (Ayan et al., 2022).

Therefore, while edge technologies' production and operational phases contribute to biodiversity loss, their application also presents significant potential to mitigate this impact, fostering more sustainable practices.

The biodiversity footprint within this analysis is expressed using the 'potentially disappeared fraction of species' (PDF), as recommended by Verones et al. (2020). The PDF metric denotes the potential fraction of species that might disappear, with a range between 0 and 1. A PDF value of 0 indicates no impact on biodiversity, while a PDF of 1 suggests the potential total disappearance of all biodiversity. To calculate the biodiversity footprint, the depths of water, nutrient, and carbon footprints (inclusive of energy use) are expressed in PDF terms. These values are then aggregated to derive the total biodiversity footprint.

4.3 Interpretation

The results of the environmental impact assessment, reflected by the sizes and depths of the various footprints, need to be comprehensively interpreted to guide actionable conclusions and strategies. These footprints, when analysed, inform us about the scale and depth of the environmental pressures and impacts exerted by last-mile connectivity and edge technologies (Fang et al., 2016).

A pivotal part of this process involves conducting a sensitivity analysis, which explores the robustness of the results to variations in assumptions and methodologies. By altering each input parameter in isolation, such as emission factors or water usage rates, we can discern their individual effects on the outcome, a method often termed as one-at-a-time (OAT) sensitivity analysis (Saltelli et al., 2007).

A second step in sensitivity analysis focuses on the global sensitivity analysis, where we consider interactions between different input parameters. Such analysis is particularly relevant when our assessment incorporates multiple footprints that are interconnected, such as energy and carbon footprints (Saltelli et al., 2007).

The goal is to align the results of this interpretation phase with the study's initial objectives. Such an alignment allows us to ensure that the environmental footprints of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies are adequately managed to align with planetary boundaries, thus informing more holistic and sustainable decision-making (Vanham et al., 2019; Heijungs et al., 2014).

5 Social impact assessment

5.1 Social Life Cycle Assessment method

Social Life Cycle Assessment (Social LCA or S-LCA) is a methodology used to assess the social impacts of products or services throughout their entire life cycle (UNEP/SETAC, 2009). The goal of social LCA is to evaluate the social aspects of sustainability, including human rights, labour rights, health and safety, and community impacts (UNEP/SETAC, 2009). Social LCA can help companies, policymakers, and other stakeholders identify social risks and opportunities associated with a product or service and identify opportunities for improvement (Jørgensen et al., 2010). Social LCA is a valuable tool for evaluating the social sustainability of products or services and identifying opportunities for improvement. It can help companies and other stakeholders make informed decisions that take into account the social impacts of their products or services.

In general, S-LCA consists of four phases: setting the Goal and Scope (G&S) of the study, collecting data (Life Cycle Inventory), assessing the risks and potential impacts (Impact Assessment) and interpreting results (Interpretation). Because different S-LCA methods have diverging purposes and applications, this chapter describes the basic principles of the four phases and the methods. The same principles and steps will be applied to the application of S-LCA within the XGain project.

5.1.1 Goal and scope

In this first phase of the S-LCA, the purpose and the methodological framework of the study are determined.

5.1.1.1 Goal definition

The goal of an S-LCA study specifies why the study is conducted. The goal of an S-LCA can be, for example, to get more insights into the social impact of a product/service, to examine potential social improvement options along the life cycle, to identify hotspots of a product and/or organization, and to quantify the social performance of a product/service (UNEP, 2020).

In the goal definition, the target audience also needs to be defined. It needs to be determined whether the study is intended for internal or external use. Ideally, the goal of the study also specifies whether to align it with attributional or consequential thinking, which will impact other methodological choices (UNEP, 2020).

5.1.1.2 Scope definition

In the scope definition phase, the functional unit, reference flow, product system, system boundaries, activity variable, cut-off criteria, data access, stakeholder categorization, impact assessment method and impact (sub)categories, indicators and data collection strategies are defined. All these items are explained in detail in UNEP guidelines for S-LCA. (UNEP, 2020).

The functional unit defines quantitatively the object of a study, for example, 1 kg of beef. In the same way as the reference flow, product system and system boundaries are defined in E-LCA. An activity variable is used as a measure of process activity which can be related to process output (UNEP, 2020). They reflect the share of a given activity associated with each unit process. Subsequently, the impact assessment method, impact (sub)categories and performance indicators will be described in more detail.

5.1.1.3 Determination of stakeholder categories, Impact Categories and Impact (sub)categories

A stakeholder category is a group type which can be affected by the activities or organizations involved in the life cycle of a product, service or organization under consideration. The UNEP (2020) guidelines include the

following stakeholder categories: workers, local communities, value chain actors, consumers, society and children. The selection of stakeholder categories also affects the choice of impact categories and subcategories at each step of the life cycle.

The main rule is that all relevant stakeholders and impact categories should be considered in an S-LCA study (UNEP, 2020). There is a wide variety of impact (sub)categories and performance indicators adopted for assessing social impacts for each stakeholder category. The selection of the impact (sub)categories depends on the method, data availability and specific contexts. Table 2 presents a list of stakeholder categories and impact (sub)categories which are included in the UNEP Guidelines (UNEP, 2020).

Table 2: Impact categories in Social LCA (UNEP guidelines, 2021)

Stakeholder categories	Worker	Local community	Value chain actors (not including consumers)	Consumer	Society	Children
Impact (sub)categories	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Access to material resources	Fair competition	Health and safety	Public commitments to sustainability issues	Education provided in the local communities
	Child labour	Access to immaterial resources	Promoting social responsibility	Feedback mechanism	Contribution to economic development	Health issues for children as consumer
	Fair salary	Delocalization and migration	Supplier relationships	Consumer privacy	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts	Children's concerns regarding marketing practices
	Working hours	Cultural heritage	Respect for intellectual property rights	Transparency	Technology development	
	Forced labour	Safe and healthy living conditions	Wealth distribution	End-of-life responsibility	Corruption	
	Equal opportunities/discrimination	Respect for indigenous rights			Ethical treatment of animals	
	Health and safety	Community engagement			Poverty alleviation	
	Social benefits/social security	Local employment				
	Employment relationship	Secure living conditions				
	Sexual harassment					
	Smallholders including farmers					

	Child labour	Access to immaterial resources	Promoting social responsibility	Feedback mechanism	Contribution to economic development	Health issues for children as consumer
	Fair salary	Delocalization and migration	Supplier relationships	Consumer privacy	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts	Children's concerns regarding marketing practices
	Working hours	Cultural heritage	Respect for intellectual property rights	Transparency	Technology development	
	Forced labour	Safe and healthy living conditions	Wealth distribution	End-of-life responsibility	Corruption	
	Equal opportunities/discrimination	Respect for Indigenous rights			Ethical treatment of animals	
	Health and safety	Community engagement			Poverty alleviation	
	Social benefits/social security	Local employment				
	Employment relationship	Secure living conditions				

The final set of impact (sub)categories can be selected by using a top-down and/or bottom-up approach, as advised by Kruse et al., (2009). The top-down approach identifies impact (sub)categories which focus on internationally recognized societal values (ILO, Human rights), whereas the bottom-up approach identifies impact (sub)categories on (but should not be limited) industry or stakeholder interests and/or data availability (Kruse et al., 2009). The top-down approach can be followed by a sectorial social risk analysis, which aims is to complete the UNEP (2020) recommended list of impact (sub)categories through an extensive identification of social and socio-economic topics that are related to the studied sector. The bottom-up approach requires actors' consultation for the prioritization of relevant impact (sub)categories. Since socioeconomic impacts have the potential to vary between industries due to the nature of the process or product with which a given industry is involved, this participatory approach is designed to gather information about the social significance of the list of impact (sub)categories from the top-down approach for directly affected and involved stakeholders within the life cycle of the product system, as defined by the S-LCA guidelines (UNEP, 2020).

When applying participatory approaches in stakeholder selection, the perspective of the different stakeholders involved can be taken into account, making the study more locally relevant. The proposed participatory approach considers all concerned stakeholders to enable the selection of the most relevant impact (sub)categories, reflecting their values and increasing the legitimacy of the assessment (UNEP, 2020).

5.1.1.4 Defining performance indicators

A performance indicator reflects the extent of the social impact and belongs to a certain impact (sub)category. The impact (sub)categories are assessed with the use of performance indicators, of which inventory indicators link directly with the inventory of the product life cycle (UNEP, 2020). Several performance indicators may be used to assess each of the subcategories. These performance indicators may vary depending on the context of the study and the product analysed. For example, an impact (sub)category may have various performance indicators, e.g., hours of missed education, is one of the performance indicators for the impact (sub)category child labour.

The UNEP (2020) guidelines propose to use a participatory approach (i.e., an approach in which actors participate and contribute to the study or scientific process) in the selection of a final set of performance indicators. A participatory approach makes the S-LCA study more locally relevant as well as increases the legitimacy of the assessment.

The UNEP guidelines (2020) advise using focus groups, i.e., a focus group is a type of group interview organized to acquire a portrait of a combined local perspective on a specific set of issues. Focus groups with a range of actors can be used to identify relevant stakeholder groups and performance indicators. Focus groups can also be used in impact assessment when defining the relative importance (weight) of each impact (sub)category. The status of impact or subcategories is assessed by collecting data on one or several performance indicators, selected to cover the most relevant aspects of the category. Table 3 gives an example of the linkage between stakeholders, impact (sub)category and performance indicator.

Table 3: Example of a linkage between stakeholders, subcategories, and performance indicators

Stakeholder	Impact (sub)category	Performance indicator
Worker	Occupational health and safety	Number/percentage of injuries or fatal accidents in the organization by job qualification inside the company
		The company or facility has conducted a health & safety assessment

5.1.2 Life Cycle Inventory

In this second phase of S-LCA, all input and output flows are identified, as well as the social inventory performance indicators to be evaluated. The Social Life Cycle Inventory (S-LCI) is about collecting data for all unit processes within the system boundaries. The life cycle inventory consists of the inventory of all flows of the studied system normalized per functional unit (e.g., 1 kg of meat) (UNEP, 2020).

To get this inventory, we follow these steps (UNEP, 2020):

1. Divide the system under study into interconnected processes that provide products or services to one another, like fertilizer production and agricultural cultivation. This creates a flow chart, already part of G&S.

2. Determine the flow amounts for each process, usually normalized to a process output. For example, it takes 5 kWh of electricity to produce 1 kg of fertilizer. Additionally, gather information about the system.
3. Quantify the total amounts of processes and their flows for the reference flow. This is typically done using a linear relationship. For instance, if 2 worker-hours are required for 1 kg of fertilizer, then 4 worker-hours are needed when 2 kg of fertilizer is indirectly required (activity variable).
4. Collect social inventory data for all processes and flows related to the main stakeholders (performance indicators) defined in G&S. This includes information such as the workers' salaries involved in producing 2 kg of fertilizer and 5 kWh of electricity.

5.1.2.1 DATA COLLECTION AND DATA QUALITY

Data collection in S-LCA is time-consuming, requiring prioritization and estimation of activity importance. Prioritization methods include literature review, activity variables, and social hotspots. Initial analysis using software identifies hotspots, forming the core of S-LCA and guiding subsequent data collection, which can be made more specific over time in an iterative fashion (UNEP, 2020). This principle applies to the XGain project.

Activity variables

Worker-hours is the most commonly used activity variable – it consists of the number of worker-hours necessary to complete a production activity/unit process. In order to collect activity variables data, there are several approaches: site-specific data collection, the use of an S-LCA dedicated database (SHDB or PSILCA) or thought input-output. Numerous studies that utilize an activity variable tend to do so via S-LCA databases, as these databases integrate by default the calculation of activity variable data (UNEP, 2020).

Data collection

Generally, the data collection for impact assessment in S-LCA is comparable for the two impact assessment approaches, being the Reference Scale approach (RS S-LCIA or Type 1) and Impact Pathway approach (IP S-LCIA or Type 2). Data are collected at the company and product level for the stakeholder groups and subcategories (RS S-LCIA) or impact categories (IP S-LCIA), as defined in the G&S of the study (UNEP, 2020). In all cases, the collected data shall relate to the life cycle stages as defined in the product system. Site-specific and/or generic data as well as quantitative and/or qualitative data, may be used depending on the requirements resulting from the definition of the G&S phase, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: Data collection and interrelations in S-LCA (UNEP, 2020)

In S-LCA, it is necessary to identify inventory performance indicators for each selected impact category in accordance with the G&S of the study. These indicators should be compatible with the chosen impact assessment approach. Social inventory performance indicators, such as salary and number of workplace accidents, provide direct evidence of a social condition at a certain life cycle stage or process (Vanclay, 2002). The choice of these indicators determines the data that needs to be collected. Performance indicators in S-LCA can be qualitative, semi-quantitative, or quantitative, and they can be specific to a company, site, generic, primary, or secondary (UNEP, 2020).

Typical sources of data for S-LCA comprise interviews, surveys, audit results, scientific and grey literature publications, generic databases, and others (UNEP, 2020). Each of these demands' different levels of involvement in terms of methods and time from the practitioner. Therefore, depending on the goal of the study and the resources available, the strategy for data collection should be defined respectively.

Secondary data collection

Secondary data can be collected through a literature review, web search or through existing databases. This will depend on the data needs and the level of detail required. Since S-LCA is an iterative procedure, a first analysis can be conducted using a database and software to identify the social hotspots of the product system (UNEP, 2020). Examples of such databases are the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database (PSILCA) and the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB). This generic analysis can form the core of the S-LCA and be complemented with other data sources for some of the processes (foreground or background) and made more specific over time in an iterative fashion (UNEP, 2020).

Primary data collection

Primary data collection involves visiting production sites, collaborating with organizations, and engaging with stakeholders through interviews, surveys, and observation (UNEP, 2020). It is determined by hotspot assessments, data gaps, and the performance of prioritized processes. Primary data is crucial for measuring positive impacts, verifying risks, and analysing impacts. Site-specific data collection methods include document auditing, interviews, questionnaires, and participatory evaluation. The data collection strategy can be adjusted based on new knowledge, important processes, hotspots, data availability, and sensitivity analysis (UNEP, 2020).

Data quality

Data e-commerce needs to be addressed as it is fundamental to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings and to reach useful conclusions (UNEP, 2020). Currently, there is still no comprehensive guidance document addressing general data quality requirements and management for social and socio-economic data in S-LCA. Due to this, some general considerations and possible data quality management options are presented in the UNEP Guidelines 2020 where they can be taken as reference (UNEP, 2020).

5.1.3 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The third phase of the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) involves measuring and understanding the potential social and socioeconomic impacts associated with a product system. Social impact assessment in S-LCA aims to calculate, understand, and evaluate the magnitude and significance of potential social impacts throughout the product's life cycle. It is important to note that S-LCA focuses on evaluating potential social impacts rather than social impacts themselves. Potential social impacts refer to the likely presence of a social impact resulting from the activities of organizations associated with the product's life cycle and its use. The assessment of potential

impacts is supported by hypotheses that have their limitations due to the relative nature of potential impacts (UNEP, 2020).

5.1.3.1 Reference Scale approach and the Impact Pathway approach

S-LCIA approaches are classified into two main groups: The RS S-LCIA or Type 1 and the IP S-LCIA or Type 2, also depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Two main approaches in S-LCA (UNEP, 2020)

The RS S-LCIA approach can be used in case the aim is to describe a product system with a focus on its social performance or social risk. This social performance is based on specific reference points. The RS S-LCIA approach does estimate the magnitude and significance of potential social impacts (UNEP, 2020). For the RS S-LCIA approach, the data collection should contain data for creating the reference scales, data for the different stakeholder groups and the different subcategories identified as relevant for the study and (optional) collection of data for applying the activity variable or a weighting step.

The IP S-LCIA approach helps to predict the consequences of the product system, with an emphasis on characterizing potential social impacts (UNEP, 2020). This is done by assessing the potential or actual social impacts by using causal or correlation/regression-based directional relationships between the product system and the resulting potential social impacts (characterization). The IP S-LCIA approach requires the collection of data for all inventory indicators relevant to express the identified impact (sub)categories, data for the characterization factors, and optionally, data for applying the activity variable or a weighting step (UNEP, 2020).

The two approaches, RS S-LCIA and IP S-LCIA, have different histories, levels of development, and implementation. RS S-LCIA approaches are currently operational and have numerous case studies available, while IP S-LCIA studies are primarily in the research domain, although several documented pathways are applicable. The choice of the S-LCIA approach influences other methodological choices in the S-LCA process (UNEP, 2020).

5.1.4 Interpretation

The interpretation phase is built upon the requirements of ISO 14044 and it consists of the following steps (UNEP, 2020), also depicted in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Elements in the interpretation phase of an S-LCA (UNEP, 2020)

Completeness check

The completeness check involves determining whether all the necessary data required to conduct an assessment is available (UNEP, 2020).

Sensitivity and data quality check

Sensitivity analysis is employed to evaluate the impact of changes in the system, such as including or excluding a unit process, on the results. In quantitative sensitivity analysis, a change of 1% or 5% is typically considered significant. Sensitivity analysis can also be applied to qualitative data to estimate the influence of including a process on the overall outcome. During data collection, it is essential to conduct a data validity check to ensure that the collected data fulfils the quality requirements for its intended application (UNEP, 2020).

Consistency check

The consistency check aims to verify the appropriateness of the modelling, collected data, and methodological choices made at each life cycle stage following the defined G&S of the study (UNEP, 2020).

Materiality assessment

In the Interpretation phase, the materiality assessment identifies significant social performances, impacts, risks, stakeholder categories, and life cycle phases of processes based on the study's G&S. Materiality is independent of an organization's influence on different phases of the product system under study and refers to the relevance and importance of a social matter in substantially influencing the study's conclusions, decisions, and subsequent actions (UNEP, 2020).

Conclusions, limitations, and Recommendations

Conclusions and recommendations should be drawn based on the study's G&S. Preliminary conclusions should be checked for consistency with the study's requirements, and if inconsistencies arise, previous steps may need to be revisited. If the preliminary conclusions are consistent, transparent reporting of the results can proceed, ensuring that all assumptions, rationales, and choices made during the study are identified (UNEP, 2020).

5.2 General idea of applying S-LCA in XGain

The idea is to apply S-LCA to all the use cases in the XGain project. Therefore, 6 S-LCAs need to be performed. For every use case, the goal & scope needs to be determined. For the selection of the stakeholder categories and impact subcategories in XGain, a combined top-down and bottom-up approach can be used in order to develop a defensible suite of performance indicators, which integrated internationally recognized impact subcategories and the perspectives of affected stakeholders (Kruse et al., 2009).

First, a top-down approach will be used to select the impact subcategories and stakeholder categories that are relevant for the XGain use cases. Based on expert judgement, the impact subcategories which are not relevant to the scope of the study can be deselected. Tables 5 through 10 (found in Chapter 8) present a first idea of the most relevant impact subcategories for the specific use cases. However, this is not a final selection; it needs to be checked and possibly revised when performing the S-LCA for these use cases.

Subsequently, a bottom-up approach will be used in which the stakeholders will be consulted to identify the key impact subcategories out of the selection made with the top-down approach. This is the actors' consultation process for the prioritization of relevant impact subcategories.

In the XGain project, the aim can be to select the 3-5 most relevant impact subcategories for the use cases. Based on the results of the top-down and bottom-up approach, it needs to be decided whether, per use case, different impact subcategories will be assessed or whether the most relevant impact subcategories overall will be assessed for all the use cases. The latter will enable comparability between the results of the use cases.

When the final selection of the impact subcategories has been agreed upon, the performance indicators will be developed based on literature and data availability. Data will be collected via both primary and secondary data collection. For the primary data collection, the stakeholders of the XGain use cases will be consulted. This can be done via a survey or an interview if possible. Secondary data sources can be S-LCA databases (such as the PSILCA and SHDB databases), as well as literature and statistics.

Depending on the selected impact sub-categories which need to be assessed, an impact assessment method can be chosen, i.e. RS S-LCIA approach or IP S-LCIA approach. The RS approach is operational for all 40 impact sub-categories. The IP approach is limited to potential social and socio-economic impacts for a single stakeholder category (workers) and for a very restricted number of impact subcategories (UNEP, 2020). Therefore, the IP S-LCIA is not suited for broad application in the XGain project, while the RS approach is. The use of a mixed methodology (i.e. combining RS S-LCIA and IP S-LCIA approach) can be explored. The application of the mixed methodology depends on the selection of the impact subcategories per use case and data availability.

6 Economic impact assessment

6.1 Benefit analysis (BA) approach

An economic impact assessment examines the effects of a measure, an event or a technology on the economy in a region, whether it is a small-scale area or a large entity, even the globe as a whole. It identifies changes in the business revenue, business profits, personal wages, and/or jobs. The economic assessment includes the observed or measured implementation trajectory of the business elements and technology involved. Such an analysis is usually conducted when there is public concern about the potential impacts³.

A basic understanding of economic benefits is necessary for understanding how the economy is functioning. As we are in the early stage of implementing or developing a business opportunity, we do not expect to have much measurable economic impacts. Here we go further, and we map the benefits and relate them to different economic readiness levels (see D2.2).

6.2 Benefits linked to the Economic Readiness Level (EcRL)

The process of digitization, with its enhanced connectivity and the adoption of new edge technologies, will greatly impact the economic landscape. To assess the economic benefits then, we rather talk about the economic readiness of these (business) technologies. We then assess their progress across nine distinct EcRL levels.

In deliverable D2.2, we defined these levels, and here we offer a brief overview of the Economic Readiness Levels.

Level 1: The first level marks the basic understanding of the economic implications and potential benefits of digitalization, connectivity, and edge technologies. At this stage, stakeholders recognize the potential for cost reduction, increased efficiency, and job creation but have not yet developed practical applications or models.

Level 2: The development of economically viable concepts and applications begins. These may include cost-effective solutions or business models that harness the potential of digitalization, connectivity, and edge technologies to drive economic growth.

Level 3: A proof-of-concept demonstration emerges that showcases the economic benefits of these technologies, highlighting the potential for job creation and market opportunities.

Level 4: Contains a validation of economically viable components and processes, assessing cost-effectiveness and return on investment (ROI). This is a crucial step in determining the feasibility of implementing these technologies on a larger scale.

Level 5: Involves validation of economically viable components and processes in a relevant environment, such as successful pilot projects or market testing, including evidence of the potential for real-world application and success.

Level 6: A demonstration of the system or technology occurs in a relevant environment, integrating economic considerations such as scalability and market penetration strategies. This stage demonstrates that the technology can be successfully adopted and scaled up.

³ <http://www.enviromineinc.com/economic-benefit-analysis>

Level 7: Sees a system or technology prototype that demonstrates economic performance in an operational environment. The emphasis is on cost reduction, increased efficiency, competitive advantage and showcasing the technology's potential for widespread implementation.

Level 8: A complete system with economically viable features is emerging, and qualified through tests and demonstrations. This stage includes market acceptance and user satisfaction, indicating that the technology is poised for successful integration into the economy.

Level 9: Represents a proven and deployed system or technology with demonstrated economic benefits and viability in an operational environment. At this stage, digitalization, connectivity, and edge technologies contribute to economic growth and development, solidifying their role as key drivers of the modern economy.

In short, the nine levels of economic readiness represent our framework for evaluating the economic potential and impact of digitalization, connectivity, and edge technologies. As these technologies advance through the levels, they gain economic viability and ultimately contribute to economic growth and development.

6.3 Interpretation

Similar to the social impact analysis, we will conduct a sensitivity and data quality check. Sensitivity analysis is about evaluating the impact of changes in the system, such as potential revenues and jobs. We described in Chapter 4 that in quantitative sensitivity analysis, a change of 1% or 5% is typically considered significant. Sensitivity analysis, which applies to qualitative data as well, will be used to estimate the economic benefits. A data validity check will ensure that the collected data fulfils the quality requirements, suitable for the intended application (see UNEP, 2020). A consistency check verifies then the appropriateness of the data included and also the methodological choices made.

6.4 General idea of applying economic impact assessment in XGain

In each use case, the objective is to pinpoint the economic benefits linked to the connectivity and edge technologies, utilizing the BA approach. The following phase of the assessment pertains to relate these economic benefits with the EcRL. Tables 5 to 10 (found in Chapter 8) present an initial selection of the anticipated economic impacts at two levels: level 1 tied to the connectivity and ICT installation, and level 2 associated with the services enabled by the connectivity and edge technologies.

7 Interoperability analyses

As introduced in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3, the multifaceted challenges of digital sustainability were explored, emphasizing the crucial need to address the impact of interoperability on digital sustainability. This is particularly necessary for *enabling effective integrated sustainability impact assessments*, which in turn aid in navigating the complex landscape of heterogeneity- including structural, semantic, and system variances.

An in-depth assessment, as well as the state-of-the-art available commercial off-the-shelf solutions of last-mile and edge computing technologies, is provided in Deliverable 3.1 of this project. While communication technologies are characterised by *access technologies* and *transport technologies*, edge processing enablers are elaborated in aspects like *computing*, *virtualization*, and available *Artificial Intelligence* solutions. The interoperability analyses will mainly focus on data that flows through these technologies, which are assumingly available in different data source systems. The notions of data hubs and data spaces will be considered as relevant for data sharing, while analysing existing information standards for data messages. The landscape of information standards in the agri-food domain, such as robotics, is diversified and continuously evolving.

Interoperability is a multi-dimensional concept with various facets, extending beyond semantics to encompass elements such as system, syntax and structure. It is central to digital sustainability as it defines the capability of computer systems or software to exchange and utilize the information produced for and by environmental and socio-economic impact assessments. As technologies evolve, they potentially become more global, cross-disciplinary and multicultural and therefore become more complex to interoperate. This leads to increasing heterogeneity issues and requires clear solutions to address these issues within information systems (Sheth, 1999).

7.1 Interoperability in Europe

The European Commission takes interoperability carefully into consideration for investments and policy developments to support digital sustainability. For example, the Commission has published the Interoperable Europe Act Proposal that should introduce “a structured and co-owned EU cooperation framework⁴”, with the following pillars: (1) a board that is co-owned by the Member States to develop common strategic agendas for cross-border interoperability, support for implementing interoperability and progress monitoring, (2) interoperability assessments that are mandatory to evaluate the (cross-border) impact of changes in IT systems, (3) a portal that serves as a one-stop-shop for interoperability solutions and, (4) measures that support innovation and experimentation, such as sandboxes.

Some efforts from the public administration are underlying this act, such as the Open Source Observatory (OSOR) that promotes collaboration, sharing and the use of Free and Open Source software within communities. Another mentionable example in public administration is the European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA), which provides a metamodel with common terminology for people that are working in the domain of public administration. The EIRA consists of architectural building blocks that are needed to build interoperable e-Government systems⁵. Additionally, the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) promotes consistent data flows and services for European public administrations. The EIF Framework includes principles, such as inclusion and accessibility, security and privacy, transparency, etc., and interoperability layers, such as governance, legal,

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/publications/interoperable-europe-act-proposal_en#details

⁵ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/european-interoperability-reference-architecture-eira/solution/eira/release/600>

organizational, semantic and technical⁶. These existing frameworks, including architectural building blocks and principles, might be of interest to the XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment.

As part of the EIF, interestingly, the Interoperability Maturity Tools (IMTs) for digital public services encompass practical tools, such as the Structural Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit (SIQAT) to assess the maturity of structural interoperability, available for any organization and citizens interested. Especially the owners of digital public services can evaluate the service for its⁷ :

- “Shareability: It is the extent that an open standard enables prospective coexistence of an off-the-shelf asset in a given domain set of digital public service value chains.”
- “Reusability: It is the extent that an open standard enables the coexistence of an off-the-shelf asset in a given value chain of a digital public service.”

As part of relevant available material such as the Interoperability Maturity Assessment of a Public Service (IMAPS), a conceptual model is proposed with different surveys to assess digital public services' interoperability maturity, including specific survey versions for legal, organizational, semantic, and technical. The IMTs contain the following five levels of interoperability maturity (Table 4).

Table 4: Five levels of interoperability maturity as defined by IMTs (reference: About Interoperability Maturity Tools (IMTs) for Digital Public Services⁸)

Levels	Name	Description
Worker	Ad hoc	Poor interoperability – the digital public service cannot be considered interoperable
Level 2	Opportunistic	Fair interoperability – the digital public service implements some elements of interoperability best practices
Level 3	Essential	Essential interoperability – the digital public service implements the essential best practices for interoperability
Level 4	Sustainable	Good interoperability – all relevant interoperability best practices are implemented by the digital public service
Level 5	Seamless	Interoperability leading practice – the digital public service is a leading interoperability practice example for others

Lebreton & Legner (2007) proposes the interoperability impact assessment model (IIAM), which has a clear focus on the business impact (economic). The model is adopted for the holistic approach and illustrated in Figure 8, including the social and environmental dimensions.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

⁷ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/interoperability-maturity-tools-imts-digital-public-services/about>

⁸ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/interoperability-maturity-tools-imts-digital-public-services/about>

7.2 Design challenges in agri-food

The use cases within XGain are assessed holistically (environmental, social, economic) concerning the impact that the introduction of digital technology will cause, both from level 1 (connectivity and edge technologies) and level 2 (information technology services). Both of these levels are somehow connected to the paradigm of the Internet of Things (IoT). While the IoT paradigm is shifting to the Internet of Everything (IoE), cross-domain interoperability is expected to become a vital driver for the realization of future digital technologies across domains such as farming, cities, automotive, etc. (Kalatzis et al., 2019). Cross-domain interoperability requires a systems-thinking approach, which means considering, for example, the governance system both externally and internally. Digitalization can improve the governance system with more transparency, access to information and efficient public administration. On the other hand, digitalization itself also requires governance, such as agreements on data ownership, sovereignty and preserving privacy. Systems thinking requires careful attention to, besides the system of study, other systems components, such as ecology, society, economy, actors, and resources, to mention a few. Changes in actors' interactions with the system's components are factors that should be considered in the analyses. Therefore, a common architectural view is needed to conduct comparative analyses of the use case.

Different initiatives aim to address some of the aforementioned governance challenges in so-called data spaces (Nagel and Lycklama, 2022). The agricultural data space, including its sub-domains, should provide the necessary architectural drivers for the interoperability and sovereignty of data (Falcão et al., 2023; Roussaki et al., 2023). Besides having data interoperable as assessment criteria for use cases, from a project perspective, there are (research) data that might also require governance. For example, the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) is expected to provide insights into the use cases through a dashboard. The insights are derived from various data sources that might be developed within different project tasks and use cases. Arguably, the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of these data are of paramount importance. Arguably, heterogeneity of data sources is a precursor for interoperability and harmonization within systems of systems. In this case, research data is generated within innovation systems (such as XGain) and operating systems on the use case level. A notable example of an operational system is the Farm Management Information System (FMIS).

Overall, shared meaning and shared understanding of data is a benefit that is also called semantic interoperability. This is achieved mainly through data harmonization and standardisation. Semantic models are seen as a potential tool to achieve this shared understanding between computers and humans (Bilbao-Arechabala & Martinez-Rodriguez, 2022; Brewster et al., 2023; Palma et al., 2022)⁹. These studies suggest this potential, while it is arguable if the design pattern takes the social aspect sufficiently into account. Could semantic models provide more understanding for humans? Although the issue of semantics and interoperability remains a point of attention for data-sharing within European innovation projects and information systems, the environmental and social impacts are insufficiently addressed.

To understand these aforementioned concerns more in-depth, as part of the holistic approach, a more systemic literature search is needed, which will help us understand interoperability on the socio-environmental assessment. In section 7.3, current, limited approaches are shortly introduced, while section 7.4 presents the steps for the literature search.

⁹ <http://divine-project.eu/objectives>

7.3 Design mechanisms

Decisions that are made in an early stage have a significant impact on sustainability (Ramani et al., 2010). The combination of different design paradigms could develop an understanding of design science. Paradigms such as eco-design, product design, life cycle assessment, etc., will be part of the holistic impact assessment across services that use cases in XGain address (mainly level 2 of the system boundaries). One of the key challenges to combining these paradigms is semantic interoperability as a success factor for designing these services.

The impact on interoperability could provide more understanding of the services that are designed and developed and addressed within use cases. These services run on web-based applications and impact the ways that farmers access, retrieve, and extract information. To make sense of the information, the text must be disambiguated and made understandable for end-users. In Navigli and Velardi (2005), a method called Structural Semantic Interconnections (SSI) is proposed in contrary to the Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) method, which is a traditional AI problem. It is found that approaches to model semantic interconnections shift from knowledge representation techniques to statistical machine learning algorithms. These algorithms could be applied to semantically disambiguate sentences and words in generic texts.

An example of these generic texts are thesauri and classification of agricultural practices as part of ontologies, and could, as an example, contribute to identifying drivers of stock changes in soil organic carbon (Fujisaki et al., 2023). The identification of these drivers plays a vital role in global challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss. To identify the semantic challenges in soil organic carbon, the DATA4C+ thesaurus has been proposed comprising 224 defined and classified terms related to land management practices in forestry and agriculture. The thesaurus is published on Agroportal to enhance fair (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles for users, such as scientists and policymakers in the domain of soil organic carbon.

For example, Davarpanah et al. (2023) devised a knowledge model that delineates the interconnections between socioeconomic and environmental systems through an ontology, enabling a comprehensive impact assessment. The model is called Sustainable Development and Climate (SDC) and will allow relevant stakeholders, such as governments, to assess the integrative impact of the changes based on their planned actions.

From an interoperability perspective, Lebreton & Legner (2007) proposes the interoperability impact assessment model (IIAM), which has a clear focus on the business impact (economic). The model is adapted for the holistic approach and illustrated in Figure 8, including the social and environmental dimensions.

Figure 8: An adapted version of the interoperability impact assessment model (IIAM) with social and environmental impact assessments as part of the holistic approach

7.4 Literature search

The aforementioned design methods, materials, challenges, and mechanisms provide a preliminary understanding of the concept of interoperability and the assumingly importance of semantics. However, a comprehensive literature search is needed to gain sufficient knowledge that is sound and valid.

Existing articles that address multidimensional, holistic and integral approaches to assess impact will be analysed to synthesize evidence on holistic impact assessments. Furthermore, the approach will be based on well-known methods and the results should support practice and policy and propose future research directions (Petticrew and Roberts, 2006).

To efficiently find relevant publications on holistic impact assessment, databases like Scopus or Web of Science will be searched. The following steps will be considered:

Figure 9: Steps for the literature search as part of the holistic approach

An example of a search with keywords: (“connectivity” OR “edge” OR interop* OR impact OR “assessment”) AND (rural* OR agricult* OR crops OR livestock) AND (environmental OR social OR “economic*”) AND (holistic OR integral OR multidimensional)

Main steps (Figure 9)

1. Identify search terms: This step involves defining key terms related to connectivity and edge technologies; economic, social, environmental and impact assessment to ensure all relevant literature is captured;
2. Use of operators and wildcards to find variations or combine concepts and synonyms;
3. Limit to title, abstract and keywords;
4. Querying in different databases: The search will be conducted across multiple academic databases to ensure comprehensive coverage of the available literature.
5. Define inclusion/exclusion criteria: Clear criteria for including or excluding studies from the review will be defined. This step ensures that the review remains focused on the intended topics and research questions.

8 XGain use cases

This chapter aims to provide a brief description of the use cases, using information collected from work package 2 in XGain. Tables for each use case give a first look at the equipment and ICT installations list, the information we need for the assessment, and an initial idea of the likely social, economic, and environmental impacts. We've split these expected impacts into two levels. Level 1 covers the ICT installation and connectivity, while Level 2 covers the services enabled by these installations and connectivity, as explained in the assessment's system boundary in Chapter 3. However, the expected socio-economic and environmental impacts at level 1 are yet hard to identify at this stage.

8.1 Use Case Specifications

8.1.1 Rural Community Services (Mora la Nova, Spain)

Services: a) Drones operation in rural areas, and b) Additional services with high data rate

Short description: The testbed in Mora la Nova aims to bring 5G technologies to rural areas and encourage their use by local educational institutions, the agricultural sector and SMEs through the dedicated network and computer resources segments. A series of drones will be deployed at the pilot site and connected via 5G to the operations centre, where various services such as monitoring, and video/image processing will be carried out. The pilot site also aims to work on an economically and environmentally sustainable model for rural 5G-based networks and explore potential business models for local agriculture and SMEs looking to expand their services using drones.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts: The operation of a testbed of 5G drones can have a direct impact on the environment and the local community, and garner support from local stakeholders. The solutions developed may focus on preventing natural disasters, such as forest fires, through real-time, computer-assisted video surveillance of specific areas. The latter could raise risks concerning the privacy of humans captured unintendedly by the surveillance cameras.

Furthermore, the agricultural sector can reap significant benefits from these technological advancements. The optimization of field activities, including crop cultivation, fertilization, and pest control, can be significantly enhanced through the use of drones enabled by 5G connectivity. These drones, equipped to capture high-resolution video data, can expedite the collection and transfer of data, providing faster and more precise insights. Through the development of drone technology that is customized to relevant AI applications, real-time analysis results can be obtained and swiftly acted upon. The drone centre aims to facilitate the development of this service, making notable contributions towards environmental conservation and optimal resource utilization. In an economic context, this could translate into more sustainable farming practices, increased productivity, and overall improved profitability in the agricultural sector.

Table 5: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the rural community services use case

Expected installation and equipment	Expected information-need	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of Wi-Fi and 5G network • 5G Radio equipment • Drones equipped with 5G modems and antennas • Agricultural machines for spraying, fertilizing, and pest control? • Computer devices used by the farmer • Computer devices used by the technology provider • (Edge) Servers to host applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and sizes of base stations • Number of flight hours per day • Energy use per hour • Carbon emission • Fertilizer use per ha • Water use per ha • Yield • data-standards 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon emissions • Energy use <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology development • Societal concern on health for wireless connectivity • Exclusion of remote areas for connectivity <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation costs of connectivity • Connectivity fees 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in fertilizer use • Change in energy use • Change in carbon emissions through the substitution of some machinery work with drones • Change in nitrogen and phosphorus footprint • Change in water footprint • Change in biodiversity footprint • Yield improvement <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe and healthy living conditions • Contribution to economic development • Health and safety of – workers - from less direct contact with spraying chemicals <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved efficiency with interoperability mechanisms • Operational efficiency and cost savings • Increased productivity • Improved profitability

* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.1.2 Remote Community (Isles of Scilly, United Kingdom)

Service: a) Precision Agriculture and b) Tourism

Short description: This use case addresses the problem of limited network coverage on the remote Isle of Scilly (UK). 5G technology and balloons/drones will be deployed to improve network coverage and demonstrate the

digitisation and precision farming techniques 'n an island's small-scale vegetable farm (Scilly Organics). The goal is to extend the tested and validated solutions to the entire island, ensuring 100% coverage and providing local and currently disconnected communities with access to services for agriculture, land maintenance, recycling and other areas. The cost of equipment for the demonstration will be covered by the project, but an operational business model with funding from the local municipality or mobile network operators will be established. The project also explores cross-sector business models between agricultural activities and tourism needs.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts:

The use of cylindrical devices to provide 5G coverage for temporary data collection introduces notable environmental, social, and economic impacts.

Environmentally, these devices contribute to land conservation by eliminating the need for mobile mast construction. They also aid in reducing carbon emissions, as they enable farmers to collect detailed sensor information remotely, reducing the necessity for physical field visits.

From a social perspective, these cylindrical devices boost safety measures by offering robust 5G communication, even in the most remote areas. This increased connectivity works to prevent isolation and promote inclusivity within rural communities.

Economically, these devices present several advantages. First, they offer cost savings, as they circumvent the need for land-consuming mobile masts and minimize travel requirements for farmers collecting data. Secondly, they have the potential to increase productivity, as the real-time and detailed data collected can enhance decision-making in farming operations, possibly leading to higher crop yields. Lastly, by providing robust 5G coverage in remote areas, these devices contribute to the improvement of digital infrastructure, which can attract more businesses to these areas, stimulating local economies, and potentially fostering job creation.

Table 6: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the remote community use case

Expected installation and equipment	Needed information	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balloons/drones for 5G network extension Soil, water and meteorological sensors Computer devices used by the farmer Computer devices used by the technology provider (Edge) Servers to host applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number and type of drones/balloons used Number and sizes of base stations Number of flight hours per day Energy use per hour Carbon emission <p>Other factors about precision agriculture depend on available data</p>	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon emissions Energy use <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote inclusivity within remote areas Concern on health for 5 G connectivity <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation costs of connectivity 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Change in energy use Change in carbon emissions through the substitution of field travel Change in biodiversity footprint Possible improvement in yield Change in efficiency with interoperability mechanisms <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology development Health and safety of workers/consumers/local community Safe and healthy living conditions

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connectivity fees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to economic development • Working hours • Smallholders including farmers <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost Savings: reduction of land use and travel expenses. • Increased Productivity: detailed, real-time data boosts farming efficiency. • Improved Connectivity Infrastructure: robust 5G coverage in remote areas attracts businesses, stimulating local economies.
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* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.1.3 Farming and Forestry (Lithuania)

Service: a) Precision Agriculture, and b) Forest Management

Short description: This use case explores deploying a 5G network in an arable farm in Lithuania to improve crop health and nutrient composition assessment using innovative crop assessment technology based on drones/planes and hyperspectral cameras. This use case aims to provide hybrid solutions of local and edge- or cloud-based solutions to efficiently handle data transfer from areas with limited internet connectivity, such as agricultural fields or forests. The use case added value is to enable near-in-situ analysis and near-real-time decision-making, reducing the use of chemicals and fertilisers in agriculture and improving the efficiency and rapid evaluation of some forest monitoring data. The demonstration scenario is based on the power of the 5G technology, where collected data can be sent directly from the drone to the server (cloud), after being pre-processed with onboard technologies.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts: The utilization of drones to gather hyperspectral data from crops offers a comprehensive overview of their health and facilitates recommendations on optimal care practices. This approach could potentially decrease the reliance on chemicals and fertilisers, subsequently reducing their negative impact on soil, water, and natural habitats in the long term. Economically, this technological implementation leads to cost efficiency by enabling a more targeted application of fertilizers and chemicals, resulting in significant savings. Additionally, the improvement in crop health through precise care can increase yields, thereby raising a farmer's income. From a social perspective, the reduction in the use of chemicals and fertilisers contributes to healthier local ecosystems, significantly benefiting local communities and positively affecting their livelihoods.

Table 7: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the Farming and Forestry use case

Expected installation and equipment	Needed information	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy lifting drone • Hyperspectral imaging camera • 5G installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of installation • Number and sizes of base stations • Number of flight hours per day • Energy use per hour • Carbon emission • Chemicals used per hectare • Fertilizer use per hectare 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon emissions • Energy use <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote inclusivity within remote areas • Concern on health for 5G connectivity <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation costs of connectivity • Connectivity fees 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in fertilizer /chemical use • Reduction in energy use • Reduction in carbon emissions through the substitution of some machinery work with drones • Change in biodiversity footprint • Change in water footprint • Change in nitrogen and phosphorus footprint • Yield improvement <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology development • Health and safety of consumers • Health and safety of workers – from less direct contact with spraying chemicals • Safe and healthy living conditions • Contribution to economic development • Working hours <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost efficiency: targeted use of fertilizers and chemicals facilitates notable savings • Improved crop health: healthier crops through precise care can result in increased yield, thereby raising a farmer's income.

* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.1.4 Livestock and Farming (Flanders, Belgium)

Service: a) Livestock health and b) Farm management

Short description: The "digital shepherd" aims to address the digital divide between extensive and intensive livestock farming in Flanders, Belgium. The solution involves using a camera system and drones to monitor herds in small pastures and remote areas. The goal is to develop a service that can be adapted to different farming ecosystems and provide real-time monitoring services that ensure animals are constantly observed, relevant events are captured for the farmer, and targeted alerts are generated. The solution aims to improve productivity and welfare and reduce stress for the farmer. The demonstration will show the application on farms with solid network connectivity and poor network conditions. The cameras and drones will be equipped with connectivity to generate alerts and analytics tailored to the specific application, in areas with strong and poor network coverage.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts:

Incorporating drone technology for livestock monitoring in small pastures presents potential economic benefits along with environmental and social ones. The adoption of this approach could enhance animal health and welfare, reduce stress for both farmers and animals and deter overgrazing in natural areas. Moreover, it is poised to engender a positive ripple effect across the meat production chain by offering consumers transparency concerning grazing locations and animal health indicators.

Table 8: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the Livestock and Farming use case

Expected installation and equipment	Needed information	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RFID antenna • Water flow sensors • Temperature sensors • Edge Processing Device • Cameras and drones • 5G or 4G installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number and type of drones/cameras used • Number of flight hours per day • Energy use per hour • Carbon emission • Population density 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon emissions • Energy use <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity skills, and digital literacy to understand connectivity <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional economic growth • Increased regional competitive advantage • Implementation costs of connectivity • Connectivity fees 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in energy use • Change in carbon emissions through the substitution of field travel • Change in biodiversity footprint <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical treatment of animals • Clear data governance including digital literacy • Health and safety of workers – less stress • Transparency within the value-chain • Health and safety for consumers

			<p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved competitive advantage for Flanders as a region • Livestock health: improved monitoring leads to healthier livestock, more efficiency, and fewer vet costs. • Farmer efficiency: less time on monitoring allows more focus on crucial farm tasks. • Consumer trust: transparency in meat production can boost demand via increased trust.
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* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.1.5 Water quality evaluation solution For Aquaculture farms in low connectivity areas (Dalmatia, Croatia)

Service: a) Water quality monitoring, and b) Remote oyster farming

Short description: The Dalmatian region in Croatia, characterized by remote coastal and open sea areas, suffers from underdeveloped ICT infrastructure. This lack of connectivity is particularly challenging for the under-digitized oyster farming industry, which needs to innovate in the face of climate change.

Currently, inefficient, costly, and time-consuming manual data collection is the norm, especially in rural areas where connectivity is limited. XGain offers a solution, providing networking and data collection services that can optimize human resources, reduce costs, and enhance management efficiency.

Moreover, XGain's real-time updates and forecasting services promise to create a more sustainable business environment. They offer potential benefits including increased operational efficiency, improved production quality, cost reduction for farms, and enhanced quality and lower prices for consumers. Importantly, the XGain solution can scale from nearshore areas to regions with even more limited data transmission availability.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts: The innovative convergence of satellite internet services, Internet of Remote Things technology, and underwater sensors, can bring about an economic revolution in the remote areas where oyster farming is prevalent. The digitalization of this sector streamlines resource management and curtails operational expenses. It reduces energy consumption by minimizing the need for regular on-site visits and quickly identifying malfunctioning sensors, which in turn, scales down the carbon footprint. The transformation also has positive social impacts as it enhances worker safety, reduces labour-intensive tasks, and contributes to local economic stability by fostering a more efficient and sustainable oyster farming industry.

Table 9: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the Water quality evaluation solution For Aquaculture farms in low connectivity areas use case

Expected installation and equipment	Needed information	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN • Satellite comms • Satellite IoT network • Sensors • Stations / gateways floating on water • Float/buoy aid • Servers (on-premise and cloud) • Digital devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of installation • Number of sensors • Energy use • Water quality • Population density • Minimum maximum wage 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon emissions • Energy use <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection and digital divide of remote coastal and open sear areas • Improved production quality <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimize human resources • Enhance management efficiency • Increased regional competitive advantage • Implementation costs of connectivity • Connectivity fees 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving water quality • Reduction in costs • Reduction in energy use • Change in carbon emissions • Change in energy use • Change in biodiversity footprint <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and safety of workers • Technology development • Working hours • Smallholders including farmers <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource efficiency: streamlining management saves operational costs. • Energy savings: reduced site visits and quick sensor troubleshooting lower energy consumption. • Local economy: enhanced efficiency and sustainability bolster local economic stability.

* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.1.6 e-Health robot assistant in Central Macedonia (Greece)

Service: a) A E-Health robot that will act as a virtual caregiver for the elderly, b) High data rate services, and c) Tourism

Short description: The E-Health Robot aims to serve as a virtual caregiver for the elderly, providing monitoring and advice. The service offers interventions aimed at improving well-being, including cognitive exercises, nutritional guidance, physical exercises, and social recommendations (online workshops). These interventions are projected through a mini-projector and assisted through a speakerphone, which can receive user commands

and provide spoken feedback. The projected interventions include daily insights, memory-enhancing quizzes and games, nutritional advice, and recommendations to promote socialization.

Expected environmental, social, and economic impacts: This initiative for the Central Macedonia region, with its focus on 5G and connectivity technologies, promises to yield notable environmental, social, and economic benefits. Environmentally, it advocates sustainable digitalization, adopting connectivity solutions that respect local needs and the diverse topography, promoting resource efficiency and reduced emissions.

Socially, it emphasizes enhancing the well-being of residents, particularly the elderly. By introducing an eHealth Robot, interactive CAP Coach Services, and enabling social interaction via technology, the project aims to boost social engagement and digital literacy in the community.

Economically, it seeks to strengthen the region's digital technology industry and rural development. The provision of targeted digital services and 5G connectivity can greatly benefit regional SMEs, stimulating modernization, export growth, and collaborations with R&D institutions. Furthermore, addressing the digital needs of the tourism sector and the general populace can positively impact the local economy.

Table 10: Socio-environmental expected impacts and relevant indicators for the e-Health robot assistant use case.

Expected installation and equipment	Needed information	Expected* impacts at level 1	Expected* impacts at level 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-Health Robot Mini-projector Speakerphone Camera Server (for processing emotion recognition) 5G connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of robots (including projector and camera) Number of robot users Type of speakerphone Type of camera Number of devices 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respect local needs and the diverse topography, promoting resource efficiency and reduced emissions Energy use Carbon emissions <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concern on health for wireless connectivity Employment of workers <p><u>Economic</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation costs of connectivity Connectivity fees 	<p><u>Environmental:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Change in carbon emissions Change in Energy use Change in water footprint <p><u>Social:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virtual caregiver for elderly Social benefits/social security Community engagement Promoting social responsibility Technology development <p><u>Economic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of costs for a human caregiver Privacy Sovereignty Local economic growth: catering to digital needs in tourism and the general populace will stimulate the local economy.

* The roster of indicators provided may be subject to minor adjustments as we continue to gather more comprehensive data and enhance our understanding of its availability.

8.2 Use cases prototypes selection for the analysis

For conducting a comprehensive environmental, social, and economic impact assessment in Deliverable D4.4, we will select specific prototypes from the potential variations of the use case base scenarios. Here, the 'base scenario' refers to the main scenario already outlined in the XGain proposal and detailed in the use case specifications section. For certain use cases, this might include only one scenario, which is the base scenario. The selection of these prototypes for D4.4 will hinge on factors such as data availability and the scenario's relevance to the impact assessment.

Here follows the list of possible alternative scenarios for the Spanish use case:

- **Audiovisual (generic):** Use drones to capture images of a region to produce videos about infrastructures, landscapes, etc. This could be tied to the tourist sector or specific events that require dissemination.
- **Engineering & Topography:** Air-based assessment of topographies, buildings, structures, etc. Useful for planning projects and reviewing the status of infrastructures.
- **Wind turbines:** Close-up, remote inspections of wind turbines for maintenance and safety checks.
- **Drone spraying (pesticides):** High-precision spraying reduces costs, time needed and the amount of pesticides used.
- **Emergency and rescue:** Using drones with (thermal) cameras to search for missing persons, identify sources of fire, etc.
- **Precision Farming:** Obtain relevant information from the terrain (maps, type of vegetation, type of soil, etc.) to plan subsequently an optimized use for farming, e.g., via optimized irrigation.

9 Conclusion and recommendations

This Deliverable 4.3 sets a methodological blueprint for examining the environmental, social, and economic impacts of last-mile connectivity and edge technologies. By analysing different use cases, we have built a foundational understanding of the benefits and challenges associated with the adoption of these technologies across several sectors.

This comprehensive methodology delineated throughout this deliverable is designed to assess both potentially negative and positive impacts. Critical issues such as job displacement, privacy, environmental sustainability, and anticipated economic benefits have been thoroughly considered.

The XGain integrated sustainability impact assessment approach presented within the document proposes tools such as environmental footprint analyses and Social Life Cycle Assessments (SLCA), aimed at evaluating the environmental and social impacts. Furthermore, it includes economic impact assessment methods, such as economic benefit analysis and economic readiness levels, for future scrutiny of the economic implications of these technologies. Finally, the methodology includes interoperability design methods, materials, challenges and mechanisms as well as a literature search to develop a framework to assess use cases and their interoperability.

Adopting this multifaceted methodology is expected to lead to a holistic understanding of both immediate and cumulative impacts within the broader socio-economic context. This broad perspective not only captures the range of impacts but also provides valuable insight for informed future decision-making and strategy formulation.

While this document, Deliverable 4.3, sets forth the methodological blueprint, the next step in this task, Deliverable 4.4, will be applying this methodology to conduct a comprehensive impact assessment. The insights obtained from this process will be instrumental in identifying best practices, exploring potential areas for improvement, and shaping the evolutionary roadmap forward for the use of 5G and related technologies across various sectors.

10 References

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